

Predicting Mental Wellbeing Indicators

Shek Armanul Haque^{1*}, Md. Mortuza Ahmmed²

¹Undergraduate Student, Department of Computer Science, American International University-
Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, American International University-Bangladesh,
Dhaka, Bangladesh

Corresponding E-mail: 24-59529-3@student.aiub.edu

Abstract

Mental wellbeing plays essential role in day to day life including academic performance .But mental well being depends on many factor such as sleep duration ,screen time,exercise,study time,energy level,daily biological clock and other related factor.Many research have done on base of clinical data by WHO,NIH,NIMH.But These research done by non-clinical data.There is limited research using non clinical data using student lifestyle data.The purpose of study is to predict student mental condition . Data collected by Various types of student in different range by Google Docs.Data collected 26 student of different age group (1st year to 4th year) student asked non harmful question. Numpy ,pandas to categorise and normalization data and Matplotlib to visualize data. There has been a strong correlation between cgpa ,study hour ,Sleep time with stress level.These researchers demonstrate how these factor affect mental health. These model help to understand depression at early stage to decline risk of mental problem by using some data.Linear regression has been used in model to train data.The study support students to maintain healthy lifestyle and promoting healthier lifestyle.

Keywords: Mental wellbeing, Student behaviour, Lifestyle factors, Linear Regression, Data analysis, Non-clinical dataset, Wellbeing prediction